

CREATION OF SYNERGETIC EFFECTS IN THE PROCESS OF ENTERPRISES MANAGEMENT AND OPPORTUNITIES OF THEIR PURPOSEFUL USE**Kelbiyev Y.,***Doctor of economic sciences,
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ASOIU, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The article studies the theoretical aspects of synergistic effects, which are considered important competitive advantages, and considers methods for achieving positive synergistic effects in the conditions of development of a modern enterprise. It also analyzes the essence of synergistic effects created in economic processes, studies their connection with synergy, which is considered a measure of their joint impact, and notes the importance of creating the basic principles of a synergistic strategy for enterprise management. The possibilities of targeted use of emerging synergistic effects in the process of enterprise management are shown.

Keywords: innovative economy, enterprise management, synergetic effects, synergism, antagonism.

1. Introduction.

In modern conditions, a new science - synergetics and the synergistic effects that manifest themselves as a result of its application in economic processes are of great interest. Synergetics is a science about the complex study of specific systems consisting of numerous components or subsystems that interact with each other in a complex way [1]. In other words, it is the mutual interaction of various elements of an economic system, which leads to dynamic effects and nonlinear development.

It is known that modern economic systems are characterized by their complexity, nonlinearity, uncertainty, openness and dynamism. Therefore, it is almost impossible for enterprises to achieve maximum efficiency in their economic activities only through the optimal use of their existing resources. As noted, the nonlinearity, uncertainty and imbalance of economic development processes (this is sometimes also called the "3 main factors" in the literature) leads to the emergence of a wide range of synergistic effects in the economy, the timely detection and purposeful direction of which directly contributes to increasing the efficiency of the economic activities of enterprises.

For this reason, the correct use of various synergistic effects manifested in the management processes of enterprises has become a necessary fact in order to increase the pace of economic development. Because the management of the emerging synergistic effects by controlling economic processes is the basis for the successful development of each enterprise. Therefore, in modern conditions, the traditional tasks of qualitatively updating the mechanisms of production and management of economic systems, while gaining relevance, require different conceptual views in the economy and an increase in the number of scientific research works in this direction. Also, in recent years, the problem of determining competitive advantages in the world, methods for increasing the efficiency of enterprises and ways to implement them, has made the issue of studying synergistic effects much more relevant and important.

2. Statement of the problem.

It is already a proven fact that only by taking into account the impact of synergistic effects on economic processes and using them purposefully, it is possible to build an efficient, competitive, innovative and socially oriented, more diverse economy. In economics, a synergistic effect is understood as the fact that the total results of the activities of a single economic system exceed the sum of the results of the activities of enterprises before their merger into a single economic system [2].

The qualitative aspects of synergistic effects in economic systems have been studied in detail by Russian researchers A. Antufyev, V. Atopov, D. Ayurov, V. Bezdeneshnykh, E. Galeeva, N. Galiyarova, R. Evstighneev, L. Evstighneeva, D. Egorov, V. Kabanov, B. Kuznetsov, E. Pugacheva, T. Solovey, E. Porezanova, as well as Ukrainian scientists S. Doroguntsov, A. Ralchuk, D. Chistilina etc. [3].

3. The essence of synergistic effects.

It should be noted that so far there is no single universal approach to accurately determining the essence of synergistic effects. It is for this reason that there are various scientific ideas and theoretical approaches in economics. For example, according to professor I. Adizes, "*The synergistic effect is the effect of increasing the efficiency of the innovative activities of integrated enterprises, taking into account the use of various types of financial instruments and their interaction*" [4].

Professor J. Bernard believes that "*...the synergistic effect characterizes the sum of the properties of individual components of the economic system, the volume of properties that allow them to exceed their sum*" [5].

Researcher L.Z.Abdokova claims that the synergistic effect manifests itself due to the "system effect" (i.e., the emergence of new features of the emerging economic system) [6].

In recent years, a different opinion has been formed that the synergistic effect is the final result of increasing the efficiency of the enterprise's business process on the basis of the interaction, integration and

combination of different economic relations into a strong, coordinated system [7]. Referring to the above, it can be concluded that “... *the synergistic effect is a universal category that includes a number of aspects, especially economic aspects*” [8].

Currently, synergistic effects are classified from different perspectives. Professor I. Ansoff, who is considered a classic of economic synergetic in the world, identified the following specific types of synergistic effects [9]:

- commercial (in cases where goods are supplied through the same distribution channels, their logistics are managed by the same enterprise or stored in the same warehouse);
- operational (as a result of higher utilization of production and personnel, sharing of additional costs, advantages of common training areas and in the case of large volumes of trade);
- investment (as a result of joint use of plant equipment, common raw materials, transfer of engineering work from one product to another, as well as the operation of common equipment);
- management (this type of synergism determines mainly a positive effect, and here the management factor is reflected in a number of profit components).

For the first time in the literature, I. Ansoff expressed the positive synergistic effect as “ $2+2=5$ ” and the negative synergistic effect as “ $2+2=3$ ”. For example, the first expression can be explained as follows: “Since the activity of individual elements in joint activity gives greater results, the qualitative measurement of

the effect obtained exceeds the quantitative indicator measured by the sum of all individual components” [10]. At this point, the difference between traditional economics (the normal condition of $2+2=4$) and synergistic economics becomes more obvious.

Unlike I. Ansoff, Professor V. Purshe classifies synergistic effects in 3 different directions [11]:

- universal (such effects are usually inherent in any rational purchasing enterprises with competent management and the necessary resources);
- specific (available only for certain enterprises and usually manifest themselves among organizations operating in a characteristic industry segment);
- unique (since they can be obtained in special operations, their systematization and classification is a rather complicated process).

There are other classifications of synergistic effects. For example, based on the number of interacting objects, the following groups of synergistic effects are distinguished [12]:

- binary (when two subjects participate in the economic relationship);
- trinary (when 3 subjects participate);
- tetranar (when 4 subjects participate in the relationship);
- multifactorial (the economic relationship is related to enterprises with a system of related entities operating in the same structure).

Depending on the location of the subjects where the interaction occurs, the division of synergistic effects into different categories is given in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Categorizing synergistic effects

Source: Compiled by the authors using [13].

Thus, the classification of the manifested synergistic effects is wide and diverse. Of greatest interest is the division of synergistic effects into financial and operational forms, since they reflect the impact of various financial instruments aimed at increasing the efficiency of the innovative activity of the enterprise.

4. Synergism and antagonism.

Recently, in the economic literature, information has been found about the following types of synergistic effects (in other words, synergism) [14]:

- Operational synergism - arises due to the integration of marketing, accounting and sales services,

strengthening the position of the manufacturing enterprise in the sales market, product brand and economies of scale, and saving on operating costs;

- Financial synergism – manifests itself through savings resulting from certain changes in funding sources and costs.

If the scope of influence of operational synergism includes a reduction in management and commercial costs, savings in the costs of conducting research and experimental design work, an increase in sales volumes, etc., then financial synergism is characterized by a reduction in financial costs for attracting debt capital, an increase in the profitability of investment projects, and the possibility of freeing up tax payments.

In the modern world, there is an urgent need to select and implement ways to improve the efficient operation of enterprises in order to achieve competitive advantages, which is determined by the expediency of a wide range of synergistic effects arising in economic processes.

As we know, the main goal of interaction between enterprises based on the integration of economic processes is to obtain a synergistic effect from joint activities. Because the creation and operation of integrated structures can be considered expedient only when a positive and stable effect is achieved. For this reason, enterprises consider the purposeful use of the effects manifested in synergistic management processes to be an important factor for economic development and labor efficiency, as well as the development of the economy.

As noted, the synergistic effect is a result of joint (collective) or purposeful (individual) influence. True, when grouping separate elements, the synergism factor may not appear. Also, this manifestation can lead to not only positive, but also negative consequences. For example, modern equipment purchased by any enterprise cannot fully demonstrate its production potential, since the existing personnel training and qualification indicators are insufficient. Therefore, the accumulation of the efforts of each employee of the enterprise is an important factor in achieving a positive synergistic effect.

Since synergistic effects reflect the dynamics of the development of unstable economic conditions, in

which variable influences lead to negative consequences, various synergistic effects arise in economic systems where stability turns into variability (or vice versa).

Recently, in foreign economic literature, one often comes across a review of the issues of achieving synergism, which is considered a source of competitive advantage as a result of the analysis of the process of implementing diversification of production. The results of theoretical and applied research on synergism have been widely covered in the works of many domestic and foreign scientists, including G. Haken, G. L. Azoyeva, R. Ansoff, O. S. Vikhansky, I. N. Dobronravova, N.V. Kudenko, G. I. Malinetsky, A. P. Pankrutina etc. economists. It should be noted that these researchers mainly study the characteristics of the effective functioning of integration processes and enterprise structures, methods for financing the production process and assessing the effectiveness of the application of synergistic effects.

Thus, the term "synergism" is used to describe the combined effect of multiple factors acting individually that is greater than the additive sum of their effects, as opposed to the term "antagonism" which is used to describe a combined effect that is less than the additive effect [15].

The possible sources of synergistic effects are shown in fig. 2.

In recent years, the volume of research on the formation of scientific and methodological principles for managing the development of enterprises and other production structures in the context of the complexity, uncertainty and dynamism of the external environment in the economy has also increased. On the basis of numerous studies on individual management systems, relevant scientific concepts are created. However, only a small part of them takes into account the main radical changes, is based on scientific knowledge and the latest methodological approaches.

5. Creation and differences of synergistic effects.

Synergistic effects in the economy are extremely diverse. They can be classified according to various characteristics. According to the time factor, the effects are divided into the following [17]:

Figure 2 Possible sources of synergistic effects

Source: Compiled by the authors using [16].

By “temporary synergistic effect” is meant the fact that economic processes at the micro level of management or in the economy as a whole lead to temporary changes in the system. In this case, there may be cases of both improvement and deterioration of the system's performance.

The concept of “trend synergism” is more complex and long-term than temporary synergism. But this does not mean that the economic system under consideration is already in equilibrium. A permanent synergistic effect can also lead to positive and negative results. In this regard, sustainability in the economy should not always be understood as a positive effect.

Because there are also permanent negative synergistic effects. For example, permanent interruptions in the activities of an enterprise as a result of a violation of its work rhythm lead to negative economic consequences.

Failure to meet the deadlines for the delivery of raw materials and materials on time first leads to a trend

synergistic effect, and then results in permanent negative consequences for the development of the enterprise, which is the “phase of emergence” of the negative synergistic effect.

From the point of view of the quantitative indicator, there are differences between monosynergetic (single, few) and polysynergetic (branched, numerous) processes. Monosynergetic processes include processes in which synergistic effects occur only once. For example, a single deficiency in the supply of raw materials at an enterprise (reduction in production volumes, loss of yield, decrease in profits, etc.) can cause a negative monosynergetic effect. Polysynergetic effects, on the other hand, manifest themselves more often. It should be noted that since polysynergetic effects are mainly observed in the economy, they directly affect the management aspects of the enterprise.

As we know, when there are constant interruptions in the supply of components and fuel for the manufac-

tured product, the volume of production and sales revenues at the enterprise are significantly reduced. This negatively affects all performance indicators, makes it impossible to purchase new innovative equipment and leads to a decrease in the level of wages of employees. These facts are ultimately reflected in the “outflow” of labor (transfer to other enterprises).

According to the optimality criterion, there are optimal and non-optimal synergistic effects. Optimal synergism is an ideal combination of system elements that results in the efficient operation of the system. Its types are: initial, desired, discrete, pre-optimal and fully optimal synergism.

Nonsynergism - in other words- antagonism. In the economy, certain (partially determined), risky (under conditions of risks) and uncertain (under conditions of

complete uncertainty) forms of nonsynergism are found.

Desynergism is a decrease in the synergistic effect as a result of the influence of various factors (external, internal, economic, social, political, legal, psychological, etc.).

Resinergism is the opposite synergism, reflecting the disruption of business relations in the economy. For example, at the end of the 20th century, negative political and social factors led to the collapse of the USSR. This resulted in the disruption of existing economic relations between enterprises and ultimately led to a deep crisis.

Quasi-synergism is an apparent synergism. Its positive type is creative, and its negative type is destructive. In this case, the synergistic effect is in an “inflated” form. In the modern economy, such synergistic effects are sometimes found. For example, outwardly, an enterprise supposedly operates on the basis of improved technology and produces a new product. However, since the management achieves these indicators by fraud, distortion of facts, etc., the expected positive synergistic effect eventually turns into a negative effect. As a result, the economic situation of the enterprise does not improve, but rather worsens.

Taking into account the above-mentioned results, the causes and consequences of the emergence of synergistic effects in the economy are shown in the table below.

Table

Causes and consequences of synergistic effects in the economy

Causes and consequences of occurrence	Possibility of synergistic effect	Signs of synergistic effect	Type of synergistic effect
1	2	3	4
Structural deformations in the economy	high	negative	nonsynergism polysynergistic
Severing existing economic ties between enterprises	high	negative	resinergism trend (or long-term)
-“Hidden” monopoly effects -Economical efficiency	high	negative	resinergism trend
-Economic crises -Recession	high	negative	resinergism polysynergetic
Poor implementation of the state regulatory process	high	negative	desynergism polysynergetic
-Inefficient operation of the enterprise - Failure to meet the delivery deadline of the product on time	high	negative	constant (steady) trend
-Unaccounted activity -Illegal transactions	middle	negative	quasi-synergism trend
-Recovering the economy -Introducing innovations	high	positive	optimal polysynergetic
-Implementation of lean manufacturing system -Saving labor costs	high	positive	trend monosynergetic
development of e-commerce (internet marketplaces)	middle	positive	desired monosynergetic
Attempts to improve product quality without increasing the level of supply of the technical base of the production process	middle	transition zone (from positive to negative)	nonsynergism monosynergetic

Source: Compiled by the authors using [3].

6. Opportunities for targeted use of synergistic effects.

Thus, in the modern economy, both negative and positive synergistic effects can arise. The establishment of the basic principles of the synergistic management process of enterprises can serve to accelerate the transformation of negative synergistic effects into positive effects. Therefore, in modern conditions, the traditional tasks of qualitatively updating the mechanisms of production and enterprise management require new conceptual views.

Conclusion.

1. Since synergistic effects reflect the dynamics of development of unstable economic conditions, where variable influences lead to negative consequences, their cration is inevitable in economic systems where stability turns into variability and vice versa.

2. In order to optimize the synergistic effects that have arisen in the economy at the modern stage of development, it is important to achieve positive synergism in the interaction of economic structures and to satisfy the condition of minimizing the negative synergistic effects that arise.

3. In the conditions of the unity of synergy and economy, the issue of establishing the basic principles of the synergistic management process of an enterprise has already become an objective reality and is awaiting its scientific solution.

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